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Humanities: approaches, contamination and perspectives

Conference proceedings, Verona 17-18th October 2019

a cura di

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Introduction

The academic disciplines falling under the definition of Humanities are the product of a long historical reflection on both method and subject of studies. Over time, scholars have renewed the interest for new factual and control-factual insights on separate fields of research, which has resulted in an impetus for deeper understanding, controversial methodological debates, and enriching discoveries. The current research within the Humanities has therefore developed in various and autonomous fields of study, which are nevertheless organized around interconnected bunch of research. As a matter of fact, specific research agendas can often lead researchers to interdisciplinary considerations, which cover different domains of knowledge. On the basis of this awareness, the international conference Humanities in the Third Millennium: approaches, contaminations, and perspectives aims to be an opportunity for reflection and discussion on the current challenges of the Humanities among young scholars and researchers.

The different research approaches adopted within the fields of Humanities share the effort of exploring the human potential which can be expressed in various forms, ranging from the comprehension of manuscripts and trans-media to the critical evaluation of ancient authors; from the study of foreign languages and literatures to the investigation of psycho-behavioural phenomena; from the development of new challenging methods to explore human history to arts and archaeological studies.

Nowadays, the Humanities are experiencing a challenging condition, as in the global marketplace of higher education, the disciplines

falling under this umbrella term are increasingly threatened by decreased funding. According to a report in *Research Trends* magazine, by Gali Halevu and Judit Bar-Ilan, international humanities funding has been in constant decline since 2009. In the United States, for instance, the financing for humanities research in 2011 was less than half of one percent of the amount dedicated to science and engineering research and development. Furthermore, in countries such as Japan, Australia, Italy and France a relative decline of about 25 percent of humanities degrees has been reported over the past few years (from Ella Delany, *The New York Times* 2013). Within this challenging academic framework, the international conference *Humanities in the Third Millennium* aims to provide young researchers with the opportunity to present their own work by encouraging interdisciplinary and transversal discussion which can lead to the evaluation of new approaches to conduct critical research in the fields of humanities.

At the beginning of 2019, the aim to create an opportunity for discussion for young PhD students of humanities disciplines has led to the organization of this conference. Under the supervision of the Doctoral School of Arts and Humanities of the University of Verona, we have assiduously worked as organizing committee to create an open, vibrant and stimulating floor for interdisciplinary discussions. This effort has resulted in the two-day international conference titled *Humanities in the Third Millennium: approaches, contaminations, and perspectives*: more than 30 speakers specialized in large number of disciplines have presented their work in front of a heterogeneous audience of students and researchers, providing important insights and food for thought on different subjects. Moments of discussion were organized in four broad thematic areas, which we believed to represent some of the cornerstones of the scientific research conducted in the fields of Humanities, namely: theoretical framework and methodology in human science; fragments and layers, hybridization and ambivalence. A call for papers organized in macro-thematic areas gave us the opportunity to encourage young PhD students to go beyond the traditional limits of their fields of research, and reflect on the interdisciplinarity and great potential of the humanities disciplines. The challenge has been enthusiastically accepted by many PhD students working in different fields of research:

arts, archaeology, philology, literature, performance studies, foreign literatures, languages, linguistics, education, philosophy and psychology. Two young researchers, Daniele Panizza and Caterina Previato, shared their experience with the audience of students and fellow researchers. This fruitful gathering of researchers coming from universities across different countries has led to the publication of the present volume, with the aim of leaving a trail of the experience lived in Verona on the 17th and 18th of October 2019.

The publication of these proceedings would not have been possible without the help and the suggestions of the Scientific Board of the conference: Professor Andrea Rodighiero, Professor Manuela Lavelli, Professor Attilio Mastrocinque, Professor Stefan Rabanus, and Professor Paolo Pellegrini. We also would like to thank our colleague Elia Marrucci as part of the Organizing Committee. A special expression of thanks is due to the reviewers who have kindly decided to take part at the blind peer-review process which have undergone the articles presented in this volume. We would also like to thank Mrs Catia Cordioli for her invaluable help throughout all the organizational steps of both the conference and the publication process and Mr Andrea Dilemmi who helped us with the design and layout of these proceedings. Lastly, particular thanks go to the all the authors and all the researchers who have attended the conference, who have made all this possible.

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The ambivalence of Stavrogin: Benjamin's reading of Dostoevsky's character as a precursor of Surrealism

by Petra Bjelica

Abstract: This paper¹ will address the problem of Stavrogin's ambivalence and Walter Benjamin's interpretation of Dostoevsky's hero in the essay *Surrealism: The Last Snapshot of the European Intelligentsia*. Stavrogin is characterized by radical ambivalence, embodying the ultimate contradiction between the evil depicted in the crime of violating a child, and the utopic dream of the Golden Age. Benjamin sees Stavrogin as a precursor of surrealism and uses him to justify evil in the revolutionary practice of Surrealists. The first objective is to analyse Benjamin's essay, to elaborate on how he understands surrealism and why he sees Stavrogin as its predecessor. Further on, I address what are the aesthetic and thematic implications of Benjamin's reading and why in his concept of Stavrogin images and language precede the self and meaning. In the end, I propose that Benjamin's Stavrogin opens other paths for understanding both Dostoevsky's writing and *Demons* from the perspective of pre-surrealist literary techniques and poetics.

Keywords: Stavrogin, Dostoevsky, Demons, ambivalence, Walter Benjamin, surrealism

A poet is not an apostle; he drives out devils only by the power of the devil².
(Kierkegaard, 1983: 61)

Nikolay Stavrogin was regarded as an enigmatic character ever since *Demons* was first published in 1871. Dostoevsky's paradoxical protagonist leaves with a sense of a silent stare from the edge of a representa-

tional abyss, provoking ambivalent feelings. Walter Benjamin's remark that «Stavrogin is a Surrealist *avant la lettre*» lucidly illuminates this issue, calling for further consideration (Benjamin, 2005, p. 214). In his essay *Surrealism: Last Snapshot of the European Intelligentsia*, Benjamin uses Stavrogin to justify evil in the revolutionary practice of Surrealists. He tries to demonstrate the need to dialectically incorporate intoxication with evil in the process of creation. In this paper, I will analyse Benjamin's reading to explore a possible new insight into «one of the most weirdly attractive creatures in world literature.» (Mann, 1945, p. XI).

Walter Benjamin never wrote an extensive critique, or a text devoted solely to Dostoevsky. Nonetheless, in *Surrealism: Last Snapshot of the European Intelligentsia*, Benjamin argues that Rimbaud, Lautréamont, and Dostoevsky are predecessors of Surrealists and devotes a paragraph to Stavrogin's confession. *Surrealism* was written in 1928 and published in 1929 in *Literarische Welt* as «a poetic, philosophic and political essay» expressing Benjamin's deep fascination with the movement (Löwy, 1996, p. 18). The first part of the essay reflects on the origins and poetics of surrealism. Later, he deals with surrealism's transformation into “poetic politics” by abandoning idealistic morality, examines conditions, and suggests methods for revolution (Benjamin, 2005, p. 216). His goal is to intoxicate the urge for a utopian revolution with poetry, to create a new future «in which action will finally become dreaming's sister». (Löwy, 1996, p. 22).

Surrealism ceases to be just another movement for Benjamin, but a new way of life infused with art. In such life, language and images take precedence over the meaning and the self, he claims. Image is a complicated epistemological and aesthetic concept in Benjamin's work. For this paper, I will use a broad definition of an image «as a potent force able to provide a frame of existential meaning» (Ross, 2015, p. 13). Benjamin doesn't connect an image with representation but with «a simultaneous, instantaneous cognition (Erkenntnis) or insight (Einsicht)» (Weigel, 2015, pp. 344-45). The essence of a surrealist experience is what he calls *profane illumination*. «Like religious illumination, profane illumination captures the powers of spiritual intoxication to produce a “revelation,” a vision or insight which transcends the prosaic

state of empirical reality; yet it produces this vision in an immanent manner, while remaining within the bounds of possible experience, and without recourse to otherworldly dogmas.» (Wolin, 1994, p. 132). These visions are also in function of inspiring emancipatory political practice. In his opinion, the idealistic morality of left-wing bourgeois emerges as the main enemy of the revolution. One of the crucial moments in Benjamin's essay, and pivotal for introducing Stavrogin, is his idea that some central features of surrealism should be understood only in contrast with this "sclerotic liberal moral-humanistic ideal of freedom" (Benjamin, 2005, p. 215). Namely, he introduces the cult of evil as a dialectical moment in overcoming naïve optimism. «One finds the cult of evil as a political device, however romantic – a device that can be used to disinfect and isolate against all moralizing dilettantism.» (Ibid., 214). Even though it might seem that Benjamin is openly promoting violence, the meander of his thinking will lead us to different currents of ideas. At this moment, he reaches for Stavrogin's confession to illustrate why this "justification of evil" expresses certain surrealist motives more powerfully than any of Surrealists. In his alchemic³ manner, he neither analyses the novel nor the chapter in detail but gives a lucid insight into the significance of Dostoevsky's character.

For Stavrogin is a Surrealist *avant la lettre*. No one else understood, as he did, how naive philistines are when they say that goodness, for all the manly virtue of those who practice it, is God-inspired, but that evil stems entirely from our spontaneity, and in it we are independent and self-sufficient beings. No one else saw inspiration, as he did, in even the most ignoble actions, and precisely in them. He considered vileness itself as something preformed, both in the course of the world and also in ourselves, to which we are disposed if not called, as the bourgeois idealist sees virtue. Dostoevsky's God created not only heaven and earth and man and beast, but also baseness, vengeance, cruelty. And here, too, he gave the devil no opportunity to meddle in his handiwork. That is why all these vices have a pristine vitality in his work; they are perhaps not "splendid," but eternally new, "as on the first day," separated by an infinity from the clichés through which sin is perceived by the philistine (Ibid, p. 214).

The most interesting part of this paragraph is the fact that Godin-inspired evil is confronted with the idealism of bourgeois, the theological dimension of evil transported on the level of political aspirations of Marxism, and the image of Stavrogin is used to reveal this contrast more deeply. Later, Benjamin enriches his reading of Stavrogin, through the letter of Count Lautréamont. Lautréamont tried to make *Maldoror*, poetic novel famous for depicting obese atrocities, seem more acceptable by bringing «...something new into this literature that, after all, sings of despair solely in order to depress the reader and thus make him long all the more intensely for goodness as a remedy. So that in the end one really sings only of goodness; but the method is more philosophical and less naïve than that of the old school...» (Ibid, p. 214). In this way, naïve dilettantism, that turns its gaze away from evil, shall be purified and shall be, paradoxically, inspired to fight against the vice. Only in this manner, the radical concept of freedom surrealist possess might «win the energies of intoxication for the revolution» (Ibid, p. 215). The conditions for revolution, further, according to Benjamin, lie in the *organisation of pessimism*⁴ – the complete mistrust into any optimism in regard to humanistic values and any type of reconciliation. The image of Stavrogin served to illuminate the issue.

But what about *Demons*? Is Benjamin true to it, or he creates an idiosyncratic interpretation that differs from the text? I argue that apart from the assertion that Stavrogin is a predecessor of surrealism, Benjamin gives neither an innovative nor a comprehensive reading. Nevertheless, this insight alone seems promising, if we consider all the rich density of the essay and try to read Stavrogin and Dostoevsky through its lens. In his characteristic manner of thinking-in-images, «that favors simultaneity and constellation over continuity, similitude over representation or sign, and the detail or fractionary (Bruchstück) over the whole», Benjamin gives a reductive and partial consideration of Stavrogin (Weigel, 2015, p. 345). Also, in highlighting the creative potential of Stavrogin's negativity, Benjamin differs from most thinkers. Both Western⁵ and Russian⁶ critics, having different perspectives or approaches, usually agree about Stavrogin's negativity, meaninglessness, void, criminality, depravity. However, some authors are highlighting

his high-moral⁷. Nevertheless, in the core of most critical approaches to Stavrogin lies the idea of a coherent character, mimetically rendered in protocols of realist fiction. The most radical reading is to see him as a character on the limit of interpretation, as a non-character based on misinterpretation (Leatherbarrow, 2000, p. 15). Russian authors⁸ are usually more concerned with the ontological rootlessness of Stavrogin's being in the scope of Eastern Orthodox Christianity. Most of them have in common treating Stavrogin as a philosophical or religious concept, neglecting his fictionality and aesthetic principles to which he is bound. Nonetheless, from whatever perspective we approach him, Stavrogin contains paradoxical elements that inspire ambivalent sensations. But what if this ambivalence lacks proper context. What if his attractiveness lies somewhere beyond or before language?

Benjamin's comparison to surrealism could provide with a new viewpoint: treating Stavrogin from a perspective beyond the representation of the self and beyond meaning. That is, to treat him not as a character from a realist novel (not even as an idea-character in Bakhtin's sense), but as a surrealist image in the way Benjamin understands it. This paper suggests it might open a new perspective on Dostoevsky's poetic and characterology, and particularly on creating Stavrogin, a hero that in its radical paradoxicality stands out from any other Dostoevsky made. Dostoevsky's famous note to himself that "Stavrogin is everything" (*The Notebooks of The Possessed*, 168, p. 270) reveals a haunting image he tried to convey through language. His way of creating Stavrogin resembles a surrealist collage⁹. Stavrogin is compiled of a long list of literary heroes or historical figures appearing like allusions or subtexts – from Shakespeare's Prince Harry and Hamlet, Byron, Pushkin's Onegin and Boris Godunov, Lermontov's Pechorin, Rousseau, Grigorij (Grishka) Otrep'ev¹⁰, a vampiric hero from Ann Radcliff's gothic novels, Dickens's Steerforth, Bakunin, Nikolay Speshnyov¹¹. These two arguments, Stavrogin being compared to an image and a collage of quotations, may be considered as aesthetical similarities between *Demons* and surrealism.

Furthermore, on the level of represented ideas, Benjamin's essay shares with *Demons* some similar problems. We find the following themes in both: role of European/Europeanised intelligentsia, revolution and role of pessimism/nihilism, need for a spiritual kernel, or re-en-

chantment of the world, and the utopian dream of paradise lost. Dostoevsky depicts in Stavrogin a vivisection of a need inflicted at a very early age by Stepan Trofimovich, an urge for «sacred anguish which the chosen soul, having once tasted and known it, will never exchange for any cheap satisfaction.» (Demons, 2006, p. 41). Evil is Stavrogin's tool to come to the point of spiritual intoxication. «Every extremely shameful, immeasurably humiliating, mean, and above all, ridiculous position I have happened to get into in my life has always aroused in me, along with boundless wrath, an unbelievable pleasure [...] If I was stealing something, I would feel, while committing the theft, *intoxication from the awareness of the depth of my meanness*. It was not meanness that I loved (here my *reason is completely sound*), but I liked the *intoxication from the tormenting awareness of my baseness*.» (my italics, Ibid., p. 693). Benjamin recognized this phenomenon and its extremely modern, surrealist level. Nonetheless, in the scope of the whole novel, Dostoevsky goes further in showing that this need itself becomes deplete and incapable of producing any inspiration. «I'm capable now as ever before of wishing to do a good deed, and I take pleasure in that; along with it, I wish for evil and also feel pleasure in it. But both the one and the other are too shallow, and never are very much» (Ibid., p. 675). As a character, if bound to the logic of Dostoevsky's text and poetic, Stavrogin doesn't completely fit into Benjamin's reading of justifying evil in the name of creation. Nevertheless, I argue that Benjamin illuminates in Stavrogin symptoms of his radical ambivalence that is slowly breaking and cracking the layers of realism. Benjamin's reading of Stavrogin warns about the need to critically disinfect our perspective.

The document of Stavrogin's confession, coming from «the need of a mortally wounded heart» as Tikhon observes (Ibid., p. 706), depicts both Stavrogin's seduction of a girl that leads to her suicide by hanging and his dream of Europe's Golden Age. I highlight two ambivalent aspects that cast a nuance of evil where it isn't usually considered. Firstly, in the scene of Stavrogin's seduction of Matryosha, the narrator clearly and repeatedly indicates something that even astonishes the hero: «her crooked smile», «kissing me terribly» and «admiration unpleasant in such a tiny child». (Ibid., p. 696). Also, Claude Lorraine's painting that Stavrogin dreams, *Acis and Galatea*, contains a violent element that

denies its idyllic paradise. Namely, two lovers are in the front in the picture. But in the back, there is the giant Polyphemus that later kills Acis out of jealousy. Both images deepen the ambivalent chasm and disturb the idealistic vision of innocence and harmony. Stavrogin is the witness to both images and he doesn't allow the ambivalence, eternally new, to be disregarded. His sharp, ruthless knowledge and self-knowledge is a product of him being a witness to it.

Benjamin's Stavrogin can represent the symbol from the essay. That is, an image of «human features for the face of an alarm clock that in each minute rings for sixty seconds» and warns about the need for wakefulness (Benjamin, 2005, p. 218) and the *organisation of pessimism*. Image of Stavrogin, if read like a warning witness of undeniable ambivalence, corresponds to how Benjamin is describing the aim of surrealism. Dostoevsky is, also, driving out the devil only by the power of the devil, as suggested by the opening quote from Kierkegaard.

To conclude, in this paper I showed that Benjamin's Stavrogin is a creation that opens other paths for understanding both Dostoevsky's writing and *Demons* from the perspective of pre-surrealist literary techniques and poetics, in which images and language precede meaning and the self. Full examination of this claim would demand another, much longer consideration of the issue.

Notes

1. INVITE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 754345.

2. It is a biblical expression from Mark, 3:15–22.

3. Benjamin writes about the difference between being a critic and a commentator of the text: «If, to use a simile, one views the growing work as burning funeral pyre, then the commentator stands before it like a chemist, the critic like an alchemist. Whereas, for the former, wood and ash remain the sole objects of his analysis, for the latter only the flame itself preserves an enigma: that of what is alive. Thus, the critic inquiries into the truth, whose living flame continues to burn over the heavy logs of what is past and the light ashes of what has been experienced.» (Benjamin, 2002, p. 298)

4. Benjamin takes this concept from Pierre Naville's essay *La révolution et les intellectuels*. «It goes without saying that he is not referring to a contemplative and fatalistic feeling, but to an active, practical and "organized" pessimism that is totally dedicated to preventing, by all means possible, the advent of the worst.» (Löwy, 1996, p. 20)

5. See Dostoevsky's *The Devils: A Critical Companion* for the selection of the most important bibliography of *Demons*.

6. See Gogina for a critical preview of Russian scholarship on Stavrogin, pp. 89–118.

7. See Saraskina, p. 310–13

8. See especially Russian religious thinkers of the twentieth century: N. Berdjaev, S. Bulgakov, S.I. Gessen, V. Ivanov, N.O. Losskij.

9. «The literary reader, on the other hand, alert above else to the fictionality of Stavrogin, will recognize that he is a highly "artificial" character, ectoplasm summoned up from the European literary tradition and trailing clouds of literary allusion.» (Leatherbarrow, 2000, p. 14).

10. A historical figure, impostor and the false tsar Dimitrij (1605–6) who claimed to be Ivan's son until recognized as a defrocked monk. Pushkin's Boris Godunov is based on these events.

11. Russian aristocrat, Dostoevsky's acquaintance, held to be one of the prototypes for Stavrogin.

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